

Participation in Decision-making and Teacher Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Ekiti State

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Abstract

The study examined the relationship between participation in decision-making and teachers job performance in secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Descriptive survey research design was adopted in the study. The population of the study comprised all 7,177 teachers and 202 principals in all the 202 public secondary schools in the sixteen local government areas in Ekiti State. The sample for this study was 384 respondents comprising 24 principals and 360 teachers drawn from 24 public secondary schools in Ekiti State. Multi-stage procedure which involved simple random was used to select sample for the study. Two instruments tagged "Participation in Decision-Making Questionnaire" (PDMQ) and "Teachers Job Performance Questionnaire" (TJPQ) were used to collect data. The instruments were validated and found reliable with reliability coefficients of 0.86 and 0.82 respectively. Descriptive statistics of frequency counts, percentages and mean were used to answer the research questions and Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that participation in decision-making was significantly related to teachers' job performance. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that Secondary school principal should ensure active participation of teachers at all decision-making levels to the extent that is possible and plausible in order to boost their morale, enhance sense of belong and increase job performance.

Keywords: Decision-making, Teachers participation, Teachers job performance,

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Introduction

Decision-making in the school system describe the areas where choice have to made concerning any issue that take place in the school. This involves the ability to identify the challenges that might arise and take appropriate steps to find solutions to the challenges. Teachers' involvement in the decision-making especially in the areas that involve their job performance is very important in the training of students academically and morally in preparation for higher education. When teachers are involved in decision-making, it gives them the opportunity to share their own ideas, it makes them have a sense of belonging and as a result they will not want the decision taken to fail. In situations where teachers are not actively involved in school governance, they may act like strangers within the school which could result in poor job performance of the teachers (Olorunsola & Abiodun-Oyebanji, 2011).

Literature Review

Concept of Decision-Making

Decision-making described the areas where choice have to be made concerning any issues related to the successful outcome of the school system. According to Mustafa (2019) decision-making is the process of selecting from available options in order to achieve desired results. Obi and Igbaseimokumo (2019), defined decision-making as a means of picking an alternate course of action, among those that are available in order to accomplish a specific goal. Ayeni (2018) affirmed that making decisions is sequential which result to a single decision that inspire or result to certain behaviour. Making decisions entails choosing a plan of action from a variety of choices. During the decision-making process, information is gathered, options are assessed, prospective consequences are considered, and then the best course of action is eventually decided.

However, there are numerous steps in the decision-making process, the first step is to identify the issue or opportunity. In order to make a decision, one must first recognize the necessity for one. This may result from a challenge that needs to be overcome or a chance that materialized. The second step is gathering information that is related to the identified issue which might require consulting with experts, the third step is developing alternatives which involves formation of potential courses of action and developing a variety of options, the fourth step is to compare the courses of action which involves comparing the course of action that will best solve the problem, the fifth step is to make a decision which involves selecting the option that best aligned with the desired objective, the sixth step involve implementing the decision by putting it into action, the last step is reviewing and evaluating in order to determine its effectiveness. This allows continuous improvement and learning from past decisions in the school system (Adegun & Ekundayo, 2023).

Decisions are very important in order to accomplish objectives or address issues in the school system. Certain factors affect decisions made in the school which are knowledge of the problem at hand, education level of those making the decision, personality of the principal, experience gathered overtime by the principal and his leadership style. In the view of this, Ossai, Okokoyo and Ezinwa (2023) opined that decision-making in the school depend on the abilities of school principals and such abilities include the ability to decide on certain difficulties, ability to work with people to choose from the options available to address challenges and achieve desired outcomes.

There are four primary areas where school principals make decisions which are planning, organizing, controlling and directing. The principal devises strategies to attain the goals of the school at the planning stage and allocates resources to carry out the strategies at the

organizing stage. At the controlling stage the principal assesses the performance plan while at directing stage he encourages excellent in subordinates to meet the goals of the school. Planning is crucial when making decisions in the school system, because it helps to make decisions easier and gives a roadmap for achieving educational goals in the school (Babalola, Nsibande & Awolola, 2019).

Decision-making in the school system is in three common manner which are; autocratic, participative and collaborative. Autocratic decision-making involves the principal being accountable and having control over every decision made in the school. Decisions taken by the principal is based on his unique experience and understanding of the circumstances surrounding the problem by which the decision is made. In autocratic decision-making, principal level of influence is high and mostly stakeholders are not involved in the decision-making when compared to participative and collaborative decision-making. Participative decision-making involves employee making an input into work related or organizational issues. The principal engages the employees in decision-making by asking them to express their thoughts, impressions and knowledge about the decision while the principal maintain control and accountability for the decision but the principal would let the employees know that their contributions have influence on the results of decision made in the school system. The principal level of influence in participative decision-making is higher than collaborative decision-making while the level of principal influence is lower in participative decision-making when compared to autocratic decision-making. When making decisions together, which is collaborative decision-making, the principal does not have exclusive control in decision-making process, school staff and other stakeholders' opinions are highly valued by the principal who recognizes that their shared goal of achieving an agreement on decisions will be of benefit to all. Decision is made from a few suggested possibilities which result to decision that is better, more transparent and widely accepted (Garcia & Vicente, 2020).

Concept of Participation in Decision-making

Participating in decision-making refers to involving people working in an organization in the process of making decisions that have impacts on them. Participating in decision-making stems from the idea that individuals who will be affected by a decision should have a chance to change that decision. Participation in decision-making is regarded as an element of democracy and effective governance. It guarantees that decisions are not taken unilaterally by a small group of people or organizations but rather take into account the viewpoints and interests of those who will be impacted by them (UNDP, 2022).

There are various benefits of participation in decision-making to both the employees and organization. According to Behraves, Abubakar and Tanova (2020), participation in decision-making helps to reduce employee's confusion regarding managerial choices and policy-making which might affect them, it helps to reassure employees that they are respected and are kept up to date on organizational difficulties which make employees have understanding of what is going on in the organization, it gives the employees the ability to change working environment of their job which make them to perform better on the job, it exposes employee to training in administrative duties in the organization, it helps to reduces the rate of employee turnover, it helps to increases efficiency of the employee as a result employee job performance is not delayed, employee are more committed and motivated to perform their job which leads to effectiveness in the organization and it improves collaboration and hence better decisions are made as a result of this, organization produce quality output.

Teachers' participation in decision-making process refers to the involvement of teachers in making decisions concerning activities conducted within the school especially the areas that involve their job performance. Ayegbusi and Ogunlade (2015), describe teachers' involvement in the decision-making process as management strategy of consulting staff on their ideas about the issues at hand, careful consideration of their perspectives before a decision is made about the issues and also using the expertise potentials of the teachers which foster a high level of loyalty. According to Ezewuzie and Eziamaka (2019), teachers participating in decision-making have many benefits when it comes to achieving school objectives because principals in secondary schools, who favour teachers input in decision making have assurance that by doing so, teachers tend to work harder, more satisfied with their job, perform more effectively, motivated and they are more dedicated to their job.

Teachers' participation in making decisions inside the school system is a suggestion of school-based management policy in which the policy is a plan to decentralize and streamline school administration by encouraging teachers to contribute to internal decisions made in the school system because teachers are crucial school human resources and their opinion is vital in achieving educational objectives (Tijani, 2020). Teachers are group of expertise that specializes in a particular field which means their contribution to internal decisions made within the school system will result to overall success of the school. According to Obi and Igbaseimokumo (2019), teachers' input into decision-making processes in schools will enhance better decision, raise student academic achievement, boost production and efficiency of the school. Ayoro and Onyeike (2020) opined that teachers' involvement in the decision-making process is important to their job performance, because teachers constitute the backbone of instruction and learning in secondary schools as decisions made but not implemented could be annoying which may prevent teachers from effectively performing their job. When school administrators promote an open channel for teachers to participate in making decisions in the school, it enhances good attitude to work, promote trust between school administrators and teachers, promote high productivity which leads to attainment of educational goals in the school. Ajetunmobi, Oladejo and Oladejo (2020) affirmed that When teachers participate in decisions regarding the delivery of their services in the educational system, their knowledge becomes broadened and this allow more collaboration and cooperation between the teachers and the school administrators. Olorunsola and Abiodun-Oyebanji (2011) opined that when teachers are carried along in decision processes, it enable them to share their ideas and ensure successful completion of the task.

One of the most crucial steps in achieving the school's goals is for teachers to participate in decision-making because teachers, unlike the school administrator have regular interactions with students and are witnesses to events taking place in the classroom and the entire school (Olorunsola & Abiodun-Oyebanji, 2011). This is in agreement with Ebinu (2020), that participation of teachers in decision-making in the school system have a positive influence on their job performance because teachers are closer to students, have significant information about the students and also understand them better while teachers' non-involvement in decision-making could lead to dissatisfaction which might affect teachers' effectiveness in performing their job and this could affect the objectives of the school. Teachers participating in decision-making in the school enables them to address issues affecting their welfare and the complaints they have about their job performance by presenting them to the school administrator. Arop, Owan and Madukwe (2019) opined that when teachers are involved in decision-making in the school, it will help to boost their confidence and as well encourage

them to fully participate in any activity. Ijaguwa, Dondo and Asen (2020) stated that when teachers are involved in decision-making, quality academic decisions are made in determining which teacher to teach a particular subject, what topic to teach, when it should be taught, selecting recent and relevant textbooks to use in lesson preparation from the variety of textbook available. Involving teachers in decision-making also entails asking them for suggestions on how to improve the situation in the school in an effort to fulfill its goals.

Concept of Teacher Job Performance

Teachers job performance could be referred to as an act of teachers carrying out an activity or task pertaining to their job. It is frequently linked to the demonstration of their skills or the outcome of their effort in the school system. Job performance can be viewed in relations to teachers' behaviour or the output produced by the teacher. Limon and Nartgun (2020) presented several hypotheses regarding job performance which can be summed up as follows;

1. Job performance is behavioural which can be influenced by external factors beyond the teacher's control because an approach of job performance that only focuses on result won't accurately reflect the contribution of teachers in achieving educational goals.
2. The evaluation of job performance indicates that the behavioural events of job performance may differ in the degree to which they contribute to organizational goals.
3. Job performance has many different aspects such as task performance, contextual performance and adaptive performance in which task performance refers to the job responsibility of the teacher while contextual performance refers to the ability of teachers to work with the school administrator which is formally not part of their job description and adaptive performance refers to ability of teachers to alter their conduct in response to demands posed by new situations in the school system.

The behavioural part of teachers' job performance in the opinion of Ekwueme, Meenyinikor and Ebete (2018) can be determined by watching how teachers behave on the job and this can be assessed by seeing how teachers perform task-related behaviors such as their demonstrations in front of the class, their understanding of the subject matter, how they teach in the classroom and their unique personal qualities, that is used to improve their knowledge, abilities and output on the job. The output part of teachers' job performance refers to the result of the teacher's behaviour. The behaviour teachers have towards their job according to Haryaka and Sjamsir (2021), in terms of timely preparation of lesson notes, showing up early in class among others may result in outcomes such as excellent students' academic achievement in both internal and external examination. However, some factors can affect the output part of teacher's job performance. For example, a teacher who have good knowledge of the subject matter, who teaches and communicate well in the classroom and prepare his/her lesson note on time which is the behavioural aspect of teachers' job performance but the students still did not perform well in the examination because of their intellectual ability or background issues such as lack of support from parent. The most important part of teachers' job performance is that it has to be directed towards achieving educational goals. Olorunsola and Oyeleye (2018) are of the opinion that teachers' job performance are duties performed at a given time in the school system in achieving school goals.

Few factors are identified that determined how well teachers perform their job. They are learners' satisfaction through teachers teaching style and quality, apart from teaching the ability of teacher to complete other tasks assigned by the school administrator, classroom management, inculcating discipline in the student, motivating students and improving

student academic performance and the interaction of teachers with students, parents, supervisor and colleagues (Ojugo & Olubor, 2021). According to Ajetunmobi et al. (2020), the outcome from the method used by teachers to complete the task assigned to them within and outside the school, when measured, reflect the expected behaviour from the teacher and he called this teacher's job performance. This means if the outcome is poor then the expected behaviour is poor but if the outcome is good, the expected behaviour is good. Chukwuaguzie, Hembadon and Akuezunkpa (2021) asserted that the job performance of teachers measures how well students performed in both internal and external examination in the school system. Student academic achievement is an important indicator of how well teachers are able to impart knowledge, skills, values, morals and the like to all student in various classes in the school. This means quality students is produced from the amount of work teachers is able to accomplished in the classroom. The quality of work that teachers do is directly related to the nature and outcome of education. The effectiveness of educational programs depends greatly on teachers' job performance in the school system.

Job performance can also be characterized as the act of completing a specific work or alternatively the capacity to skillfully combine ethical conduct with the intention of achieving organization goals (Chukwueze, 2023). Therefore, job performance is the tasks carried out by teachers at a specific time to accomplish the objectives of education in the school system. Odu-dikoro (2022) stated that teachers job performance is the ability of teachers to produce good outcomes in their students' academic achievement. Adamu, Bello and Badamasi (2019) buttressed this point by describing teachers job performance as work performed by teachers which result in manpower building of a nation from the academic outcome of students in the school system. This implies the choice of behaviour of teachers towards their job, will determine the outcome of students' academic performance and the fulfillment of academic objectives, which will have effect on manpower building of the nation. Olorunsola (2010) conclusively opined in her thesis that job performance is a function of workers ability, willingness, availability of facilities, good leadership and a conducive environment for effective performance. It can be inferred that teachers are the backbone of educational activities in the school system. Their success and failure depend on the attitude they put into their job which will bring out either positive or negative outcome that will affect the manpower of the nation. This is the reason teachers need to participate in making decisions especially in the area that involve their job performance.

The study seeks to establish the relationship between participation in decision-making and teachers job performance. It seeks to examine the extent of participation in decision-making in secondary schools. It seeks to examine joint and relative contributions of participation in decision-making variables to teachers' job performance.

The below research question was raised to guide this study:

1. What is the extent of teachers' participation in decision making in public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria?

The following research hypotheses were formulated to guide this study:

1. There is no significant relationship between participation in decision making and teachers job performance in public secondary schools in Ekiti State.
2. The variables of teachers' participation in decision making will not significantly contribute to teachers' job performance in secondary school.

Methodology

The descriptive survey research design was adopted in this study. The population of the study consisted of 7,177 teachers and 202 principals in all the 202 public secondary schools in the sixteen local government areas in Ekiti State (Source: Ministry of Education, 2025). The sample for the study consisted of 384 respondents which made up of 24 principals and 360 teachers. The sample was selected using multistage sampling procedure. In the first stage, simple random sampling techniques was used to select two senatorial districts from the three senatorial districts in the state. In the second stage, three Local Governments were randomly selected from each of the senatorial district. In stage three, 24 public secondary schools were purposively selected from the six Local Government areas. In the final stage, simple random sampling technique was used to select 15 teachers from each of the school.

Two sets of instruments tagged Participation in Co-curricular activities and Communication system Questionnaire (PCCQ) and Teachers Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ) were used to collect data. The face and content validity were done by experts to determine the appropriateness of the instruments and making sure the contents were well represented. The reliability of the instruments was established using test-retest method. The instruments were administered to the respondents twice within an interval of two weeks. The collected data were analyzed using Pearson Moment Correlation Analysis. A reliability coefficient of 0.86 and 0.82 were obtained respectively. The coefficients were considered high enough to conclude that the instruments are reliable. The descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data collected. All the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Question 1: What is the extent of teachers' participation in decision making in public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria?

In analyzing the question, mean score, frequency counts and percentages were used to illustrate the responses to items 1-30 in Section B of "Participation in Decision-Making Questionnaire (PDMQ)". Mean score on each of the item was compared the criterion benchmark mean score of 2.50. Items with mean score below the cut-off were categorized into 'Low' extent of teachers' participation in decision making in public secondary schools while those around the mean and above the criterion mean were categorized into 'Moderate' and 'High' extent of teachers' participation in decision making respectively. The extent of teachers' participation in decision making in public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Extent of teachers' participation in decision making in public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria

	Extent of Teachers' Participation in Decision Making	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	STDEV.	REMARK
1	Participation in Examination Matters	183 (50.8)	172 (47.8)	4 (1.1)	1 (0.3)	3.49	0.53817	High
2	Participation in Disciplinary Matters	107 (29.7)	167 (46.4)	75 (20.8)	11 (3.1)	3.03	0.79294	High

3	Participation in Admission Process	51 (14.4)	107 (29.7)	164 (45.6)	38 (10.6)	2.48	0.86365	Moderate
4	Participation in School Plant Maintenance	95 (26.4)	174 (48.3)	82 (22.8)	9 (2.5)	2.99	0.77014	Moderate
5	Participation in Co-curricular Activities	91 (25.3)	194 (53.9)	67 (18.6)	8 (2.2)	3.02	0.72715	High
6	Participation in Communication System	103 (28.6)	137 (38.1)	102 (28.3)	18 (5.0)	2.90	0.87299	Moderate
	Average	105 (29.2)	159 (44.2)	82 (22.8)	14 (3.9)	2.99	0.82261	Moderate

Criterion mean: 2.50

Source: Researcher computation (2025)

Table 1 presents the extent of teachers' participation in decision making in public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Using a criterion mean score of 2.50 for the rating scale, all the items had mean score above the cut-off point. This implies that the extent of teachers' participation in decision making in public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria was high.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between participation in decision making and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ekiti State.

Table 2: Participation in decision making and teachers' job performance

Variable	No of schools	Mean	SD	r	P
Participation in decision making	24	89.46	3.10	0.453*	0.026
Teachers' job performance	24	101.83	11.74		

* $p < 0.05$ (Significant Result)

Source: Researcher computation (2025)

Table 2 shows that the computed r value (0.453) is significant at $p < 0.05$ level of significance. The null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there is significant relationship between participation in decision making and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ekiti State. The correlation between participation in decision-making and teachers job performance in public secondary schools in Ekiti State is moderate and statistically significant in a positive direction.

Hypothesis 2: The variables of teachers participation in decision making will not significantly contribute to teachers' job performance in secondary school.

Table 3: Contributions of variables of teachers' participation in decision making to teachers' job performance in secondary school

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta(β)		
Constant	28.951	55.669		.520	.610
Participation in examination matters	.205	.109	.478	1.880	.077
Participation in disciplinary matters	2.821	2.283	.268	1.236	.233
Participation in admission process	.058	.090	.174	.646	.527
Participation in School Plant Maintenance	.023	.075	.080	.311	.759
Participation in cocurricular activities	3.751	2.279	.295	1.646	.118
Participation in communication system	.087	.131	.163	.666	.514
Multiple R=0.788, Multiple R²= 0.621, Adj. R²=0.487, F_{6,17}=4.637*					

***p < 0.05 (Significant Result), Dependent Variable:** teachers' job performance

Source: Researcher computation (2025)

The following regression can be derived from Table 3.

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4 + b_5X_5 + b_6X_6$$

Where

- X₁ = Participation in examination matters
- X₂ = Participation in disciplinary matters
- X₃ = Participation in admission process
- X₄ = Participation in School Plant Maintenance
- X₅ = Participation in co-curricular activities
- X₆ = Participation in communication system
- b_i = (i=1-6) Regression Weight Coefficients
- a = Constant (other variables other than X₁-X₆)

The multiple regressions relationship between the dependent and independent variables can therefore be given as follow:

$$Y = 28.951 + 0.205X_1 + 2.821X_2 + 0.058X_3 + 0.023X_4 + 3.751X_5 + 0.087X_6$$

Table 3 shows that variables of teachers' participation in decision making significantly contributed to teachers' job performance in secondary school (F_{6,17}= 4.637*, p<0.05). The null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that variables of teachers' participation in decision making significantly contributed to teachers' job performance in secondary school.

The table reveals that there is significant positive multiple correlation between the predictor variables (participation in communication system, participation in examination matters, participation in co-curricular activities, participation in disciplinary matters, participation in admission process, participation in school plant maintenance) and teachers' job performance (R=0.788, p<0.05). This implies that all the predictor variables are factors that can exert influence on teachers' job performance in Ekiti State. The value of the coefficient of determination (R²=0.621) indicates that all the predictor variables jointly accounted for

62.1% of the total variance in teachers' job performance while the remaining 37.9% unexplained variation is largely due other variables that can account for teachers' job performance in Ekiti State.

The regression result in the table shows that the most important predictor variable that contributed to the total variance in teachers' job performance in Ekiti State is participation in examination matters ($\beta = 0.478$). This was closely followed by participation in co-curricular activities ($\beta = 0.295$), participation in disciplinary matters ($\beta = 0.268$), participation in admission process ($\beta = 0.2174$) and participation in communication system ($\beta = 0.163$). The variable with the least contribution to teachers' job performance in Ekiti State is participation in school plant maintenance ($\beta = 0.080$). The calculated F-ratio (4.637) was significant at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that the predictor variables jointly provide a significant explanation for the variation in teachers' job performance in Ekiti State.

Discussion

The study showed that the extent of teachers' participation in decision making in public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria was moderate. It implies that teachers' participation in decision making (participation in examination matters, participation in disciplinary matters, participation in admission process, participation in school plant maintenance, participation in co-curricular activities and participation in communication system) is good enough to enhance teachers' job performance. What can be responsible for this finding may be the fact that government is making efforts to ensure that the teachers' participation in decision making is enhanced for effective teaching and learning.

The study equally showed that there was significant relationship between participation in decision making and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ekiti State. This implies that participation in decision making in terms of supervision, motivation, plant maintenance, decision making and evaluation will improve or have direct positive impact on the teachers' job performance. What may be responsible for this finding is the fact when teachers are involved in decision-making, it gives them the opportunity to share their own ideas, it makes them have a sense of belonging and as a result they will not want the decision taken to fail. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Akinwale and Okotoni (2018) that teachers participation in decision making in the school system have a positive influence on their job performance.

The study further showed that the variables of teachers' participation in decision making significantly contributed to teachers' job performance in secondary school. The variable with the highest contribution to teachers' job performance in secondary school was participation in examination matters. This mean to teachers' job performance, teachers' participation in examination matters is very important. The calculated F-ratio (4.637) was significant at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that the predictor variables jointly provide a significant explanation for the variation in the teachers' job performance in secondary school.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, teachers participation in decision-making in Ekiti State secondary school was inspiring. This has led to an improved job performance of teachers. The variables of participation in decision-making were important factors that contributed to job performance of teachers. This have helped to achieve the school goals and also improve student academic performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made

1. Secondary school principal should ensure active participation of teachers at all decision-making levels to the extent that is possible and plausible in order to boost their morale, enhance sense of belong and increase job performance.
2. Principals should ensure teachers participation in decision-making especially in the area that involve their job perform
3. Principals should continuously ensure participation of teachers in decision-making making in the areas of examination matters, disciplinary matters, admission process, school plant maintenance, co-curricular activities and communication system in order to maintain and improve teachers job performance in secondary schools.

References

- Adegun, O.A & Ekundayo, H.T (2023). Management Theories and Concepts. In A. Ajayi & A. Popoola (Eds) Educational Management. A Book of Readings in Honour of Prof Akin Ogunlade and Prof F.O. Olaleye. Ado-Ekiti: Interlink prints.
- Ajetunmobi, F.G., Oladejo, M.A. & Oladejo, M.A. (2020). Participatory Management, Professional Development, and Teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Ogun State, Nigeria. *Journal of Learning for Development*, 7(2); 161-173.
- Arogunade, B.B (2018). School Factors as Correlates of Secondary School Teachers' Job Performance in Ekiti State, Nigeria. *Ghana Journal of Educational Management*, 1(1); 70-77
- Arop, F.O., Owan, V.J. & Madukwe, E.C. (2019). Human Resource Management and Teachers' Job Performance in Secondary Schools in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Management Research* 5(2); 27-34.
- Ayeni, A.J. (2018). Principals' Decision-Making Strategies and Teachers' Productivity in Secondary Schools in Ondo Central Senatorial District of Ondo state, Nigeria. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research: An Administration and Management* 18(10); 18-30.
- Ayoro, R.A & Onyeike, V.C (2020). Participation in Decision-Making and Leadership Style as Determinants of Teachers' Productivity in Mission Secondary Schools in Delta State. *International Journal of Innovative Social & Science Education Research* 8(1); 64-72.
- Babalola, J.B., Nsibande, N. & Awolola, O.I. (2019). Decision-Making in Education. *Ilorin Journal of Educational Management* 38(1); 1-22.
- Behraves, E., Abubakar, A.M & Tanova, C. (2020). Participation in Decision-Making and Work Outcomes: Evidence from a Developing Economy. *International Journal Employee Relation* 42(3); 704-723.
- Chukwuaguzie, E.E, Hembadon, N.R & Akuezunkpa, E.L (2021). Occupational Stress and Teachers' Job Performance in Secondary Schools in Makurdi Education Zone of Benue State, Nigeria. *Sapientia Global Journal of Arts, Humanities and Development Studies* 4(1); 79-98.
- Ebunu, A.A. (2020). Participatory Management for Enhancing Students' Academic Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal* 7(5); 145-156.

- Ekwueme, A.F., Meenyinikor, N.D. & Ebete, S.E. (2018). Teachers' Job Enhancement Strategies for Job Performance in Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State. *African Journal of Educational Research and Development* 11(2); 230-239.
- Ezewuzie, J.J & Eziamaka, C.N (2019). Teachers' Participation in Decision-Making: A Necessity for Effective Management of Schools. *Nnadiabube Journal of Education in Africa* 3(1); 106-115.
- Garcia, I.C. & Vicente, J.A. (2020). Strategic Decision-Making in Secondary Schools: The Impact of a Principal's Demographic Profile. *Leadership and Policy in Schools* 21(2); 1-22.
- Haryaka, U. & Sjamsir, H. (2021). Factors Influencing Teachers' Performance in Junior High School. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education* 12(6); 2058-2071.
- Kumari, J. & Kumar, J. (2023). Influence of Motivation on Teachers' Job Performance. *Humanities and Social Science Communications* 10(158); 1-12.
- Limon, I. & Nartgun, S.S (2020). Development of Teacher Job Performance Scale and Determining Teachers' Job Performances Level. *Journal of Theoretical Educational Science* 13(3); 564-590.
- Mustafa, T. (2019). An Investigation into Educational Decision-Making in a Centralized Education System: Governance Principles and the Case of National Education Councils. *International Journal of Education Policy and Leadership* 15(11); 1-17.
- Obilor, E.I (2020). Teacher's Factor Influencing Students' Academic Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State. *International Academy Journal of Educational Technology and Research* 7(2); 28-41.
- Olorunsola, E.O (2010). Job Satisfaction and Gender Factor of Administrative Staff in South-West Nigeria Universities. *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Education Research, Clute Institute* 3(10); 51-55.
- Olorunsola, E.O & Abiodun-Oyebanji, O.J (2011). Teachers' Participation in Decision-Making Process in Secondary Schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education Administration and Policy Studies* 3(6); 78-84.
- Oparaji, I.C., Ugwu, I. & Chime, G. (2021). Teaching Ethics as Determinants of Teachers' Job Effectiveness in Public Secondary Schools in Okigwe Education Zone, Imo state. *International Journal of Management Studies and Social Science Research* 3(3); 275-281.
- Ossai, A.G, & Okokoyo, I. E (2023). Principals' Decision-Making Strategies and Teachers' Productivity in Delta State Secondary Schools, Nigeria. *Russian Law Journal* 6(3); 2524-2532.
- Tijani, A.A. (2020). Teacher's Involvement in Decision Making and Job Performance in Secondary Schools in Kwara State, Nigeria. *SOSIOHUMANIKA: Jurnal Pendidikan Sains Sosial dan Kemanusiaan* 13(1); 1-12.
- United Nations Development Programme (2022). Ensuring Inclusive and Responsive Decision-Making for Sustainable Development. UNDP Oslo Governance Centre – SDG 16 Policy Brief. https://www.undp.org/sites/g/files/zskgke326/files/202209/Final%20Policy%20Brief%2016%207%202_0_0.pdf

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